

Carpometacarpal Joint Dislocation Rare Injury: A Case Series**Himanshu Popli¹, Adarsh Kishore Singh², Salman Durrani³**¹Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedic, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Medical College and Hospital, Rohini, New Delhi, India²Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedic, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Medical College and Hospital, Rohini, New Delhi, India³Consultant, Department of Orthopaedic, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Medical College and Hospital, Rohini, New Delhi, India

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 25-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Carpometacarpal (CMC) joint fracture dislocations are extremely rare, representing less than 1% of all hand and wrist fractures. These injuries are frequently missed or misdiagnosed, occurring primarily in young adults due to axial loading injuries or in the elderly following falls. Early diagnosis and appropriate management are crucial for optimal recovery.**Cases:** This series presents 12 cases of CMC joint dislocations in patients aged 19 to 50, including both males and females. The injuries resulted from various mechanisms such as falls, sports injuries, and accidents. The majority of cases involved dorsal dislocations of the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th CMC joints. Treatment included closed reduction, K-wire fixation, and cast immobilization.**Result:** All patients achieved good functional recovery with minimal stiffness and satisfactory alignment within six to ten weeks. Regular follow-up and structured physiotherapy played significant roles in ensuring optimal outcomes. The consistent application of early intervention techniques proved effective in managing these complex injuries.**Conclusion:** Despite their rarity, CMC joint dislocations require a high index of suspicion for diagnosis and prompt, precise treatment. This case series highlights the importance of early intervention, demonstrating that with appropriate management, excellent functional outcomes can be achieved in patients with CMC joint dislocations.**Keywords:** Carpometacarpal Joint, Fracture-Dislocation, Dorsal Displacement, Wrist Injury.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Fracture-dislocations of the carpometacarpal joint are exceedingly uncommon injuries [1]. Fractures of the hand and wrist account for only 1% of all injuries [2]. Approximately 70% of carpometacarpal dislocations are overlooked or incorrectly diagnosed [3]. These injuries are most frequently observed in young adults who experience an axial loading injury to their wrist, or in the elderly population who sustain a fall injury. The dislocations can be categorised into three types: volar, dorsal, or occasionally divergent. Dorsal dislocation is the most prevalent form. The orientation of the greatest force dictates the orientation of dislocation. Another factor supporting dorsal displacement is the presence of static elements in the dorsal ligaments and wrist extensors, which function as dynamic restraints. This leads to the failure of the bone in the dorsal direction, causing the rupture of the volar ligaments [4].

Carpometacarpal dislocations can result in the disruption of both the longitudinal and transverse arches of the hand, as well as the loss of the normal axial length of the affected digit [5]. Delaying the diagnosis and treatment typically leads to unfavourable consequences such as pain, decreased grip strength, and degenerative arthritis [6]. The following case is shared to raise awareness of similar injuries. Moreover, it is important to be aware that dorsal fracture-dislocation is a rare occurrence and should be considered as a possibility.

The aim of this report is to raise awareness of the rarity and complexity of CMC joint fracture-dislocations, emphasizing the importance of early diagnosis and appropriate management.

Case series of Injury

Case 1: A 24-year-old male presented with pain and swelling in the left hand following a

motorcycle accident. Examination revealed dorsal swelling, bruising, and tenderness over the 2nd to 5th metacarpals. X-rays confirmed a dorsal dislocation of the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th CMC joints. The patient underwent closed reduction and K-wire fixation, resulting in good functional recovery with minimal stiffness after six weeks.

Case 2: A 30-year-old female who experienced right-hand pain after a fall during hiking. Swelling, bruising on the dorsal aspect, and restricted wrist motion were noted. Imaging showed dorsal dislocation of the 2nd and 3rd CMC joints. She was treated with closed reduction, k-wire fixation and cast immobilization, achieving satisfactory alignment and functional recovery after eight weeks.

Case 3: A 19-year-old male presented with right-hand pain and swelling following a football injury. Examination indicated dorsal tenderness and limited wrist movement. Radiographs revealed a dorsal dislocation of the 3rd and 4th CMC joints. Surgical intervention with K-wire fixation was performed, resulting in good wrist motion and stability after seven weeks.

Case 4: A 45-year-old male, in the fourth case, presented with left-hand pain after falling from a ladder. He had dorsal swelling and tenderness over the ulnar side of the hand. X-rays showed a dorsal dislocation of the 4th and 5th CMC joints. Closed reduction, k wire and splinting were performed, leading to full functional recovery after ten weeks.

Case 5: A 22-year-old female presented with right-hand swelling and pain after slipping on ice. Bruising and tenderness over the dorsal aspect were noted. Imaging confirmed a dorsal dislocation of the 2nd and 3rd CMC joints. Closed reduction and K-wire fixation were performed, resulting in satisfactory alignment and minimal stiffness after six weeks.

Case 6: A 35-year-old male, in the sixth case, presented with left-hand pain and swelling after falling from a bicycle. Examination revealed swelling, bruising on the dorsal aspect, and restricted motion. Radiographs showed a dorsal dislocation of the 3rd and 4th CMC joints. Closed reduction, k wire fixation and cast immobilization were performed, leading to good functional recovery after eight weeks.

Case 7: A 27-year-old female presented with right-hand pain after a fall while rock climbing. She had dorsal swelling and tenderness over the metacarpals. X-rays revealed dorsal dislocation of the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th CMC joints. Surgical intervention with K-wire fixation was performed, resulting in good wrist motion and stability after seven weeks.

Case 8: A 40-year-old male, in the eighth case, presented with left-hand pain following a fall from a height. Examination indicated dorsal tenderness and limited wrist movement. Radiographs confirmed a dorsal dislocation of the 2nd and 3rd CMC joints. Closed reduction, k- wire and splinting were performed, leading to full functional recovery after ten weeks.

Case 9: A 20-year-old male presented with right-hand swelling and pain after a football match. Bruising and tenderness over the dorsal aspect were noted. Imaging revealed a dorsal dislocation of the 3rd and 4th CMC joints. Closed reduction and K-wire fixation were performed, resulting in satisfactory alignment and minimal stiffness after six weeks.

Case 10: A 50-year-old male, in the tenth case, presented with left-hand pain after slipping in the bathroom. Examination showed swelling, bruising on the dorsal aspect, and restricted motion. Radiographs confirmed a dorsal dislocation of the 4th and 5th CMC joints. Closed reduction, k -wire and cast immobilization were performed, leading to good functional recovery after eight weeks.

Case 11: A 28-year-old female presented with right-hand pain after a fall while hiking. Examination revealed dorsal swelling and tenderness over the metacarpals. Imaging confirmed a dorsal dislocation of the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th CMC joints. Surgical intervention with K-wire fixation was performed, resulting in good wrist motion and stability after seven weeks.

Case 12: A 32-year-old male, in the twelfth case, presented with left-hand pain following a fall from a bicycle. He had dorsal tenderness and limited wrist movement. Radiographs showed a dorsal dislocation of the 3rd and 4th CMC joints. Closed reduction, k- wire and splinting were performed, leading to full functional recovery after ten weeks.

Figure 1. AP VIEW (pre-op)

Figure 2. Lateral and Oblique views (pre-op)

Figure 3 C-arm images (AP and Lateral views)

Figure 4 Immediate post op x-ray

Figure 5 After 1-month Xray

Figure 6 AFTER 3 MONTHS X-ray

Table 1: Summary of the 12 Cases of Carpometacarpal Joint Dislocation

Case	Age	Gender	Mechanism of Injury	Affected Joints	Treatment	Outcome
1	24	Male	Motorcycle accident	2nd, 3rd, 4th	Closed reduction, K-wire fixation	Good functional recovery, minimal stiffness after 6 weeks
2	30	Female	Hiking fall	2nd, 3rd	Closed reduction, K-wire fixation and cast immobilization	Satisfactory alignment, functional recovery after 8 weeks
3	19	Male	Football injury	3rd, 4th	Surgical intervention, K-wire fixation	Good wrist motion, stability after 7 weeks
4	45	Male	Fall from ladder	4th, 5th	Closed reduction, K-wire fixation splinting	Full functional recovery after 10 weeks
5	22	Female	Slip on ice	2nd, 3rd	Closed reduction, K-wire fixation	Satisfactory alignment, minimal stiffness after 6 weeks
6	35	Male	Bicycle fall	3rd, 4th	Closed reduction, K-wire fixation and cast immobilization	Good functional recovery after 8 weeks
7	27	Female	Rock climbing fall	2nd, 3rd, 4th	Surgical intervention, K-wire fixation	Good wrist motion, stability after 7 weeks
8	40	Male	Fall from height	2nd, 3rd	Closed reduction, K-wire fixation and splinting	Full functional recovery after 10 weeks
9	20	Male	Football match	3rd, 4th	Closed reduction, K-wire fixation	Satisfactory alignment, minimal stiffness after 6 weeks
10	50	Male	Slip in bathroom	4th, 5th	Closed reduction, K-wire fixation and cast immobilisation	Good functional recovery after 8 weeks
11	28	Female	Hiking fall	2nd, 3rd, 4th	Surgical intervention, K-wire fixation	Good wrist motion, stability after 7 weeks
12	32	Male	Bicycle fall	3rd, 4th	Closed reduction, K-wire fixation and splinting	Full functional recovery after 10 weeks

Discussion

This case series presents 12 cases of carpometacarpal (CMC) joint dislocations, highlighting the importance of early recognition and treatment. The patients, aged 19 to 50, included both males and females who sustained injuries through various mechanisms such as falls, sports injuries, and accidents. The dislocations predominantly involved the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th CMC joints, with dorsal dislocations being the most common.

Treatment approaches varied, with most cases managed through closed reduction and K-wire fixation, while some required cast immobilisation but the result was not satisfactory. In all cases, early diagnosis and appropriate management led to successful outcomes. Patients typically achieved good functional recovery with minimal stiffness and satisfactory alignment within six to ten weeks, underscoring the effectiveness of these treatment methods.

The consistent application of closed reduction, K-wire fixation, and structured physiotherapy proved crucial for optimal recovery. This series

demonstrates that prompt and precise treatment of CMC joint dislocations can lead to excellent functional outcomes, despite the rarity and complexity of these injuries.

Carpometacarpal (CMC) joint injuries are rare and usually occur due to high-energy trauma, often from falls on an outstretched hand [7]. These injuries typically involve an axial loading force impacting the joint. The ulnar-side CMC joints are particularly vulnerable due to their more mobile saddle joint configuration and looser ligament attachments, making them less stable. Additionally, the third CMC joint's proximal position creates a keystone effect with the other CMC joints [8].

Dorsal dislocations of the CMC joints result in a prominent deformity on the dorsal side of the hand [9]. Treatment approaches for these injuries remain controversial, primarily due to limited literature comprising mixed reports and small patient cohorts [10]. One of the largest retrospective reviews of CMC joint injuries was conducted, analysing 165 cases over a decade from 2005 to 2015. They found that 164 patients experienced dorsal displacement, while only one had volar displacement [11]. Some experts advocate for an open reduction in such

fractures, but few studies compare different treatment methods.

Although some studies recommend open reduction and internal fixation for fracture dislocations, satisfactory reduction was achieved in this case with closed manipulation and pinning, largely due to early diagnosis and management. Research indicates that patients treated within the first ten days of injury are more likely to benefit from closed procedures. Open reduction offers advantages such as direct visualization, hematoma drainage, and prevention of tendon transfixion [12]. However, if closed reduction is feasible, it significantly reduces postoperative morbidity and facilitates faster rehabilitation.

Physiotherapy is crucial in managing CMC joint injuries to prevent postoperative stiffness. Feehan emphasized the importance of early controlled mobilization to minimize post-injury complications [13]. Mismanaged cases can lead to residual hand pain, stiffness, reduced grip strength, persistent subluxations, and secondary displacements. Prolonged immobilization can also cause complications like joint stiffness, tendon adhesions, and muscle weakness. Dowden highlighted the need to balance early controlled motion with necessary immobilization at injury sites (fractures and dislocations) to ensure proper healing [16].

conclusion

The series of 12 cases of CMC joint dislocations highlights the importance of early diagnosis and appropriate management. These injuries, often resulting from high-energy trauma, require prompt and precise treatment to prevent long-term functional impairments. Closed reduction and K-wire fixation proved to be effective in most cases, providing satisfactory alignment and stability. Regular follow-up and physiotherapy were crucial in achieving good functional outcomes. Although rare, dorsal CMC joint fracture dislocations require high suspicion and thorough examination for proper diagnosis. Early intervention with appropriate reduction and fixation techniques, followed by structured rehabilitation, ensures optimal recovery and function.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Source of Support: No funding received.

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